

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN READABILITY, AESTHETIC PREFERENCES AND APPROPRIATENESS OF VISUAL ILLUSTRATIONS IN A DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION SETTING

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Abstract

The first part of the paper discusses the process of collecting empirical data in a rural community of the Qwa-Qwa region of South Africa in order to establish the community's views and opinions about different types of visual illustration approaches. The information was subsequently used to guide the production of visually illustrated soy-related nutrition education messages, which were distributed free of charge in the community as part of an integrated nutrition education programme. In the second part of the paper, the discussion of the data collected during three separate data collection events (n=75, n=67 and n=92) focuses on the relationship between (1) image readability, or the absence of readability barriers; (2) the visual aesthetic preferences of the members of the target group, based on the respondent's choices and verbal explanations when presented with a range of different visual illustration options for comment, and (3) the overall appropriateness of an illustration.

Keywords: Visual communication, aesthetic preferences, development communication

Introduction

The present paper deals with issues and concerns relating to the process of pre-testing visual illustrations used in educational material meant for a development communication setting. In the field of development communication, pre-testing educational messages in the target community before they are disseminated on a large scale is generally considered a *sine qua non*. As discussed in the work of Mody (1991), Boeren (1994), Brouwer (1995) and many others, pre-testing typically involves presenting a provisional version of the educational material to a sample of the target group and canvassing their reactions, views and opinions with a view to identify any possible barriers to effective communication. Pre-testing procedures fall into two broad

categories, namely those that focus on the comprehension of the message, as opposed to those that concern the appeal of the message (Mody, 1991, p. 197).

As far as the visual communication dimension of development communication is concerned, visual images such as pictograms, drawings, graphs or photographs are frequently included in the educational material in order to raise both comprehension and appeal. In other words, the intention is that the images will primarily perform a mnemonic function, or assist with the comprehension and retention of information, as well as phatic function, i.e. to attract and retain the attention and interest of the target group (Peters, 1978, p. 58; Watson and Hill, 1993, p. 139). That is not to say that the images do not perform other communicative functions and roles as outlined by Sachs-Hombach (2006, p. 262) as well, but these are generally regarded as less crucial.

Methods and procedures

Empirical data was collected in the rural Thibela community of the Qwa-Qwa region of South Africa, which borders on Lesotho. The aim was to establish the community's views and opinions about different types of visual illustration approaches. The information was subsequently used to guide the production of visually illustrated soy-related nutrition education messages, which were distributed free of charge in the community as part of an integrated nutrition education programme. The integrated nutrition education programme was funded by the South Africa Netherlands Research Programme on Alternatives in Development (SANPAD). The purpose of the programme was to explore to what extent food production and nutrition education training programmes, complemented by the implementation of soy home gardening initiatives and innovative household soy processing equipment as interventions, impact on household food security, dietary intake and food procurement patterns. A total of 212 Qwa-Qwa households participated in the programme, or a total of 1018 people, with a mean of 4.8 people per household.

The pre-testing of the visual illustrations involved the voluntary and anonymous participation of community members preceded by their informed consent. During three separate data collection events (n=75, n=67 and n=92), each participant held a ten to fifteen minutes long conversation with a field worker conducted in the home language of the participant. The three data collection events took place in the local community hall on days selected by the community leaders. The events were timeously announced by sending all participating households SMS messages, followed up by reminders on

the community radio station. During data collection, the field worker completed a short questionnaire in the presence of the respondent. The first part of all three questionnaires dealt with basic demographic information about the participant (age, home language, gender). Taken together, the second part of the three questionnaires aimed to measure (1) whether the illustrations shown to the respondents were clearly understood, i.e. whether the meaning that the respondent attached to the image was the same as the intended meaning, and (2) where the aesthetic preferences of the respondent lay. This was achieved by showing the participant a range of different illustration options, ranging from highly abstract pictograms on the one end of the spectrum to clip art, to realistically rendered shaded line drawings, to a 'straight' colour photograph on the other end of the spectrum.

The questionnaire was designed to accommodate low-literate respondents and to avoid a situation where the ability of the participant to verbally articulate complex pictorial meanings was essential. This was achieved by restricting the pre-formulated questions to the following: (1) What does this image show? and (2) The illustration style of the two (in some cases three) images is different. Which one of these do you prefer? In both cases the participant was invited to make general comments or to explain further. The field workers were trained to remain as neutral as possible during data collection, regardless of the responses encountered. At the end of the data collection day each participant received a hamper with some food as a gesture of thanks.

Results

The main finding that emerged from the questionnaire data is that clip art images as found in most standard software programmes were poorly understood in the target group and yielded a wide range of unintended meanings and interpretations. For example, when shown a clip art style image depicting soy beans together with the pod and asked 'What does this image show?', only a small percentage of the respondents (9.3%) answered either with 'soy beans' or just 'soy' or simply 'beans'. The remaining participants responded with a variety of unintended interpretations, such as apples, potatoes, eggs and even footballs. Such an unacceptably wide visual representational latitude (see Pauwels, 2005) was also the case with clip art images rendered with a cartoon-like quality. For example, a clip art style cartoon image of a salt seller with the word 'salt' written on it was not well comprehended (28% of the respondents supplied

the envisaged answer). Unintended responses included ‘it looks like a hat with the word salt written on it’, or ‘a hamburger with salt written on it to indicate that hamburgers are high in salt content’. In contrast, pictograms, shaded line drawings and colour photographs were as a general rule well comprehended.

The aesthetic preferences of the target community lay with realistically rendered shaded line drawings, as well as with cartoon-type illustrations. For example, in one of the questionnaire items the respondents were shown two images side by side illustrating the washing of hands under a tap and asked the question ‘The illustration style of the two images is different. Which one of the two do you prefer?’ The first image was rendered as a black and white pictogram with minimal detail, whereas the second illustration contained considerably more image detail (such as the thread at the end of the tap where a hosepipe can be attached) and was drawn and shaded with a high degree of realism. In this particular instance, 86.7% of the respondents chose the realistically rendered shaded line drawing.

Concluding discussion

In the light of the results obtained, the basic pre-testing categories of message comprehension and message appeal (Mody, 1991, p. 197) mentioned in the introduction of this paper do not adequately describe the actual state of affairs in this particular target community. As summarised in Table 1, and as contained in the data collected, the readability of a visual illustration, or the ease with which the viewer comprehends the intended meaning on the one hand, and the extent to which the chosen illustration approach fits with the aesthetic preferences of the target community on the other hand, do not necessarily co-vary.

Table 1. *Overview of the relationship between aesthetic preferences, image readability and appropriateness*

		Comprehension, or absence of readability barriers	
		High	Low
Appeal, or degree of fit with the aesthetic preferences of the target group	High	Appropriateness High	Appropriateness Low
	Low	Appropriateness Low	Appropriateness Low

Stated differently, the majority of members of the target community (1) indicated that their aesthetic preferences lie with cartoons, yet the intended meaning of those cartoon-style images presented to them for comment was poorly understood; (2) easily understood the intended meaning of pictograms, yet opted for realistically rendered shaded line drawings as their preferred choice as far as illustration style is concerned when asked to choose between a pictogram and a sparingly shaded line drawing; and (3) easily understood the intended meaning of realistically rendered shaded line drawings and also indicated that their aesthetic preference lies with this type of illustration approach when asked to choose between a sparingly shaded line drawing and a photograph. This means that even though the target community was pleased with cartoons, these were poorly understood, as summarised in a response along the lines of 'I don't know what it is [or what is being shown here], but to me these types of pictures are more beautiful than those'. Due to their low readability, however, the inclusion of cartoon-style images in the educational material was inappropriate. The reverse was also the case: even though the data suggest that the readability of pictograms in this particular community was high, their appeal was low and thus their appropriateness was also low.

In short, the findings of this study suggest that appropriateness requires both readability and a high degree of fit with the aesthetic preferences of the target community, but the one is not necessarily a predictor of the other.

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